

**LIQUID SILICON INFILTRATION - A FAST AND
LOW COST CMC-MANUFACTURING PROCESS**

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ABSTRACT

Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMC) offer a unique potential for structural applications in aerospace industry. Chemical Vapour Infiltration (CVI) represents the main manufacturing route, which, in general, is time consuming and costly, thus preventing a broader use for other applications.

This paper presents a fast manufacturing technology for CMC materials on the basis of liquid silicon infiltration, a well established industrial process to produce SiSiC bulk ceramic. However, instead of carbon particles, carbon fibers are used, which are embedded in a dense carbon matrix, protecting the load carrying fibers from chemical attack by liquid silicon.

By this process, all components which can be manufactured using continuous fiber reinforced polymers can be realized as CMC components, because a composite part is the first product within this 3-step process, followed by one carbonisation and one siliconizing step. Thus, a CMC component can be manufactured within a two-week period.

KEYWORDS: Carbon/Carbon; Fabric; Fiber, Graphite; Matrix, Ceramic;
Oxidation Resistance; Liquid Silicon Infiltration.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMC) are emerging as a novel material group, offering a great potential to realize high temperature stable, thin walled, highly integrated complex structures for limited life applications. Moreover, material scientists as well as ceramic design engineers expect a dramatic increase in damage tolerance compared to bulk ceramic materials. The application of CMC's in hot structures will play a key role especially in future space transportation systems due to steadily increasing demands concerning temperature stability, oxidation resistance and erosion rates, structural weight, etc.

With respect to these requirements, up to now only ceramic matrix composites like carbon fiber reinforced silicon carbide (C/SiC) and SiC/SiC promise properties which are superior to high temperature metal alloys and to carbon reinforced carbon (C/C).

2. PROCESSING TECHNIQUES FOR CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

In the literature, mainly two types of fibers are reported to be used as continuous reinforcements for CMC's, carbon fibers and Nicalon SiC fibers. Regarding high temperature oxidation stability, silicon carbide (SiC) is the best suited matrix system. The most common matrix is carbon, reinforced with carbon fibers. More than 20 years of experience exist for C/C applications.

Based on experience with C/C-processing, there are three main fabrication routes for CMC production with SiC matrix, chemical vapour infiltration (CVI), liquid infiltration and pyrolysis of organometallic precursors. All methods start with a fiber skeleton with a fiber orientation in one (1D), two (2D), three (3D) or even more directions: the higher the number, the higher the degree of isotropy and the damage tolerance of the material and the lower the allowable stress level.

2.1 Chemical vapour infiltration

The CVI process operates at relatively low temperatures between 1000°C and 1200°C. The lower the temperature, the deeper the deposition range into the material and the longer the deposition time. The higher the temperature, the higher the deposition rate and the higher the inside porosity. An in-depth porosity is unavoidable due to the fact that interior cavities will be closed by material deposited from the outside surfaces. A typical

deposition rate is about 50 μm per day, resulting in component manufacturing time of weeks and months. However, CMC materials produced with the CVI technique offer hitherto the highest mechanical values.

2.2 Liquid infiltration techniques

The most essential parameters and mechanisms governing the infiltration technique by liquid silicon are published in [1,2]. Compared to the CVI route this process needs higher temperatures in the order of 1450°C to 1600°C. In the upper temperature regime the viscosity of silicon as well as the contact angle to carbon is low. Thus, a complete infiltration of a porous C/C skeleton, driven by capillary forces only, is feasible within a few minutes. This process is very similar to the industrial production route for monolithic silicon infiltrated silicon carbide (SiSiC). It is well known that the reactivity of liquid silicon is very high. Free standing PCS-SiC fibers are completely dissolved at 1600°C within 10 minutes [2].

High modulus carbon fibers are less attacked than high strength fibers; pitch fibers or PAN based fibers are better suited than Rayon based C-fibers. Coatings can partially prevent or delay reactions between fibers and liquid silicon. The porosity of the C/C skeleton is important to realize a complete infiltration and a complete reaction of the infiltrated silicon to form SiC. The amount of porosity can be adjusted by the selection of a proper precursor material and an adequate number of reinfiltration/recarbonisation steps. A large variety in material behaviour is explicable by the large number of processing parameters.

2.3 Pyrolysis of organometallic precursors

This is an emerging technology which became feasible as soon as Si-polymers were available which can be infiltrated. In principle, this process is very similar to the C/C infiltration technique. Instead of using C-polymers with a high carbon yield, Si-polymers with a high SiC-yield are applied. The pyrolysis of those polymers occurs at about 1000°C, reducing the fiber degradation problem. On the other hand, the inherent high shrinkage of the precursors as a result of the high differences in density between polymer (about 1 g/cm³) and SiC (3.2 g/cm³) and the insufficient SiC yield of about 50-70% make several reinfiltration steps necessary [3]. Nevertheless, this process has the potential to combine the lower temperature level of the CVI technique with the advantages in shaping large and complex parts of the liquid impregnation process.

2.4. Conclusions on the basis of literature data

Combining all results found in the literature concerning bending strength tests, Fig. 1, one can clearly distinguish certain trends which can be summarized in the following statements:

- High strength values correspond with a brittle type of fracture, coinciding with a strong fiber/matrix bond.
- High strength values are reported especially for unidirectional reinforced materials (UD), which may be suitable for local stiffeners but not for skin structures.
- Only in case of high strength UD- or 1D-materials does a CVI process offer higher values compared to liquid infiltration techniques.
- Damage tolerant materials offer high strain values, calculated from the specimen deflection. These materials are characterized by a weak fiber matrix bond, high porosity, extensive crack pattern and consequently a reduced stiffness. The SiC formation is concentrated at the specimen's surfaces only.
- For damage tolerant material CVI and liquid infiltration techniques show similar strength values. The strength level of 1D-material and 2D-material is almost identical and only slightly superior to 3D carbon/carbon.
- It is impossible to combine high strength and high damage tolerance behaviour in one material. Consequently, for ceramic matrix composite one has to select either a high strength capability or a high damage tolerance behaviour. Due to the fact that technically feasible CMC materials need to have at least two directions of fiber reinforcement, which reduces the maximum achievable stress level anyhow, we decided for our in-house CMC activities to strive for a high damage tolerant material.

3. IN-HOUSE LIQUID SILICON INFILTRATION

The aim of our activity in the field of CMC's is to develop a fast low cost manufacturing technique suitable for realizing integrally stiffened structures, like leading edges or rudders for reentry vehicles, as well as for components within the hot gas stream of jet engines like vectoring nozzle flaps. Fast process means: liquid silicon infiltration with one-shot manufacturing of the fiber reinforced resin components, followed by one carbonization step and one liquid infiltration procedure, Fig. 2.

We are using a low viscosity thermoset system which allows 2D-lay-up sequences in prepreg technology, as well as injection molding technology using 2D- or 3D-reinforcements.

After carbonization the carbon yield of that system is 70%. It can be seen from Fig. 3 that in the case of a unidirectional fiber orientation (UD) this 70% residual carbon is almost free of voids and densely surrounds the fibers. The bonding between carbon fiber and carbon matrix is even too strong. The fiber pull-out effects should be more pronounced to realize a higher damage tolerance. The shrinkage parallel to the fibers is almost zero, perpendicular to the fibers about 10%. The measured open porosity amounts to 8%, mainly due to small surface cracks.

During the subsequent liquid infiltration procedure a reaction between liquid silicon and carbon takes place, however, only on the outside surface of the UD-laminate, Fig. 3, because liquid silicon could not penetrate the dense C/C. This reaction zone is limited to about two filament diameters, e.g., to about 15 μm . On one hand, that means that the oxidation protecting layer of a SiC-coating of less than 15 μm is too thin to provide real component protection. On the other hand, this effect can be utilized as a protection mechanism to avoid pronounced fiber degradation caused by chemical reaction with liquid silicon; we took advantage of the latter effect by using carbon fabric instead of UD-laminates. After carbonization the fabric material also showed a macroscopic shrinkage close to zero in fiber direction, e.g., in 0° and 90° orientation. However, in the microscopic range, in each fiber bundle shrinkage perpendicular to the filaments takes place, and due to the shrinkage impediment by the transversely oriented neighbouring fiber bundles, cracks occur around each bundle, Fig. 4. During the siliconizing procedure these cracks will be filled by liquid silicon; the contact areas will react to SiC, protecting each bundle against oxidation. Thus, the oxidation protection takes place not only at the outside surface of the material but in the whole volume around each bundle. We call that a "mosaic" structure with SiC as a "plaster" material. It is essential to note that the cracks parallel to the fibers do not propagate into the transversely oriented fiber bundles, i.e., the cracks stop, diverge and propagate parallel to the bundles, a mechanism which allows high stress levels and good damage tolerance behaviour. The state of development today is thus, that each fiber bundle is divided into three or four strands, and within the plaster there is still a certain amount of free silicon. However, we have several improvements in mind to optimize the crack pattern, as well as the fiber matrix bonding conditions in future.

4. OXIDATION TESTS IN A PLASMA WIND TUNNEL

One of the most critical requirements for materials suitable for the thermal protection system of reentry vehicles is a low erosion rate during reentry. To get preliminary information about the applicability of our material, samples of C/C, C/SiC and SiC/SiC were investigated under simulated reentry conditions in the plasma wind tunnel of the Institut für Raumfahrzeuge at the University of Stuttgart [7].

Specimens of 25 mm in diameter and 2-3 mm thickness were positioned in a plasma with a mass flow rate of 2.5 g/s (80% N₂/20%O₂) for about 15 min. at constant surface temperatures, measured by a spectral pyrometer. Prior to tests, the siliconized samples were released from free silicon to produce comparable starting conditions. By weighing before and after the tests, the specific erosion rates (related to area and exposure time) were determined. Some results of these erosion tests are depicted in Figure 5.

For C/SiC we measured in the range from 1150°C to 1500°C a quasi-linear increase in mass loss of about 10%, corresponding to a decrease in thickness of about 0.3 mm within 15 min. For higher temperatures the slope becomes steeper and after 15 minutes at 1800°C a 3 mm laminate showed a residual thickness of about 2 mm.

Comparing with the C/C material stage, the C/SiC material shows a substantially lower erosion rate because of the internal oxidation protection. As a consequence this protection scheme will be improved in future and combined with adequate surface protection.

In case of SiC/SiC the specific mass losses are quite similar to those of C/SiC, even though the curves are equidistantly shifted to some lower values.

5. FIRST STRUCTURAL COMPONENT TEST

As a first structural application of our in-house produced C/SiC material we developed a ramjet nozzle with an integrated secondary combustion chamber. Mechanical properties of the material were evaluated by means of equivalent C/SiC tubes which were tested in a hydraulic pressure test set-up at ambient temperature. The material's pseudo-plasticity could be observed which provides a certain damage tolerance, Fig. 6. The nozzle - 250 mm long, 75 mm mean diameter, 1.6 mm wall thickness and 220 g mass - was tested at an experimental ramjet test facility of the DLR in Lampoldshausen up to the thermo-mechanical limits, Fig. 7. The nozzle passed fired testing at pressure levels up to 7.5 bar successfully [9].

6. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Our in-house liquid infiltration technique is at an early stage of development. All results reported for our material are based on T300 plain weave fabrics for plates, Fig. 8, or T300 braided tubes for the nozzles. Carbonisation and siliconizing steps took place in industrial furnaces during the weekend periods. In the meantime, manufacturing equipment has been installed in-house to produce components within 380 ϕ mm diameter and 450 mm height. Today, it takes two weeks to produce C/SiC flat plates of 300 x 300 mm. Thus, the learning rate is favourably high to improve the mechanical values and the oxidation resistance of the material as well as to produce C/SiC components.

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Fig. 1 CMC-stress strain relations, global overview [4]

1) CFRP-Component

- Laminating, autoclave, injection molding
- Special precursors with high char yield

2) Carbonization

- Adapted temperature rate up to 800°C
- Microcrack pattern due to shrinkage impediment

3) Silicizing

- Liquid infiltration at ~1650°C
- $Si + C \Rightarrow SiC$ (matrix)

Alternative Processes

- 1) Chemical vapour infiltration (CVI)
- 2) Pyrolysis of silicon-polymers

Fig. 2 Production scheme for in-house liquid silicon impregnation process [5]

Fig. 3 Close view onto the surface layers of our 1D-C/C material after liquid silicon infiltration [6]

Fig. 4 Cross section of 2D-C/SiC material

Fig. 5 Mass loss versus temperature of plasma arc jet tested materials [8]

Fig. 6 Static pressure tests of C/SiC tube specimens [9]

Fig. 7 Hot-test of C/SiC-ramjet nozzle

		2D C/C	3D C/C	2D C/SiC	2D C/SiC	3D C/SiC	2D SiC/SiC
Manufacturer		Schunk	Aerospatiale	SEP	DLR	SEP	SEP
Process		Precursor	CVI	CVI	Precursor	CVI	CVI
Tensile Strength	MPa	150 - 200	110	350	86	80	200
Young's Modulus	GPa	70 - 90	31	90	60	75	230
Elongation at Break	%	0.2 - 0.4		0.9	0.2	0.5	0.3
ILSS	MPa	8 - 12	56	35	23	50	40
Compression Strength	MPa		76	420 - 580		650 - 740	420 - 580
Flexural Strength	MPa	150 - 200		500	160	300	300
Therm. Expansion	10^{-6} 1/K	0.8 - 6.9		3 - 5		1.7 - 2.3	1.5 - 3
Coefficient of Emmission			0.9	0.8		0.8	0.8
Thermal Conductivity	W/mK	15 - 80	4.7 - 22	6.5 - 14		13 - 17.5	10 - 19
Thermal Capacity	J/kgK		840	620		620	620
Porosity	%	5 - 8		10	5	12	10
Fiber Content	Vol.%	55 - 65		45	55	24	40
Density	g/cm^3	1.55 - 1.65	1.6	2.1	1.9	2.3	2.5
Max. Temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	2000	2000	1600 - 1800	1600 - 1800	1600 - 1800	1000 - 1200

Fig. 8 Mechanical properties of C/C, C/SiC and SiC/SiC with fabric reinforcement

